

CRITICAL THINKING AS A KEY FOR TEACHER SUCCESS

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Nowadays changes are taking place in the system of education. However, the main goal of lessons is still the formation of a personality who is able to perceive and analyze facts, various social phenomena and events independently and to build their worldview in accordance with the obtained knowledge. This article discusses the positive aspects of developing critical thinking in students, as well as the main methods and strategies for its development.

Key words: critical thinking, modern teacher, educational institution, professional competence, professional development, creative thinking, educational process.

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In accordance with the new Federal State Educational Standards of General Education, a teacher must be able to structure the educational process in a modern information educational environment.

The educational process in modern conditions is aimed at:

- creating experience in working with information, its application in non-standard and unusual life situations, ensuring self-development and self-actualization of students;
- formation of methods of activity applicable both within the educational process and when solving problems in real life situations.

The traditional teaching methods have been replaced by updated methods:

- "Learning through asking questions", or "guided discovery process";
- the method of diagnostic questions (the Socrates method) — answers to which allow you to see and correct the remaining incomprehensible;
- explanation tasks — the student must explain something to a classmate or teacher;
- creation by students of "memory cards", reference and other summaries in which it is necessary to isolate the main thoughts and establish the relationship between them [1, p. 19].

The requirements for the personnel conditions for the implementation of the basic educational program have also changed:

- the level of qualification of teachers and other employees of the educational institution;
- continuity of professional development of teaching staff of an educational institution.

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The purpose of professional development is to update theoretical and practical knowledge. As a result of professional development, the teacher masters' new methods of solving professional problems, improves his professional level, which is especially important in constantly changing conditions and requirements of society.

The technology of developing students' critical thinking is one of the most demanded pedagogical technologies used in the construction of a lesson in an information educational environment.

What is critical thinking? How can students develop it? Critical thinking is a natural way to interact with ideas and information. It requires skills not only to master information, but also to critically evaluate, comprehend, and apply.

The profession of a teacher is special — the future of students as citizens of the country depends on the results of our activities, how successful it will be from the right choice of profession by graduates, developing their conviction in self-improvement and constant continuation of education throughout their lives.

The main condition for teachers to successfully use technologies aimed at developing critical thinking is the teacher's own understanding and acceptance of the idea of the need to develop critical thinking. In addition, in order to teach children to think critically, the teacher must be able to do it himself. Therefore, it is necessary to develop the critical thinking of teachers.

Each teacher works at his own level of creativity, constantly improving it. At first, a young teacher is characterized by using ready-made recipes and recommendations, following the script of a lesson or event without taking into account the characteristics of the class team and its working conditions. Admittedly, this level is still devoid of creative elements.

Others are characterized by a critical assessment of methodological recommendations, they can abandon some elements of the lesson, replacing them with more effective ones for these conditions - this is a sufficient level of skill. Still others have a certain system of work. When preparing for lessons, they do not use specific developments, but general provisions and ideas — this is a high level of skill.

And the fourth is characterized by the construction of its own methodological system, which is constantly being improved based on the data of pedagogical science and advanced pedagogical experience — this is the pinnacle of pedagogical skill.

In order for a teacher to be interested in high results of educational and innovative activities, in improving his professional competence, he must have a self-evaluating activity. Adequate self-esteem and the ability to evaluate one's activities are the most important signs of conscious self-regulation of a person [2, p.11].

This type of activity requires creative thinking — thinking that allows you to use previously acquired knowledge to create new ones. A teacher should be able to think critically and correctly evaluate the results of their professional actions.

As one of the methods of streamlining the process of realizing one's professional development, one can use an algorithm consisting of questions:

1. What is the purpose of my upcoming work?
2. What is known and what should be done to find the missing information?
3. What thinking skills will allow me to achieve my goal?
4. Has my goal been achieved?

The changes taking place in the modern education system make it necessary to improve the qualifications and professionalism of the teacher, i.e. his professional competence. The main goal of modern education is to meet the current and promising needs of the individual, society and the state, to prepare a well—rounded personality of a citizen of his country, capable of social adaptation in society, starting work, self-education and self-improvement. And a teacher who thinks freely, predicts the results of his activities and models the educational process is a guarantor of achieving his goals [3, pp.7-8].

That is why the demand for a qualified, creatively thinking, competitive teacher personality capable of educating a personality in a modern, dynamically changing world has increased dramatically.

What kind of teacher should be in order to justify the trust and expectation of children and parents, in order to fulfill all the tasks of education and upbringing that modern society and living conditions set for us?

What is he like, a modern teacher?

A modern teacher is a human being:

- able to create conditions for the development of creative abilities - to develop students' desire for creative perception of knowledge - to teach them to think independently

- independently formulate questions for yourself in the process of studying the material, more fully realize their needs,

- increase motivation to study subjects, encourage their individual inclinations and talents, and much more!

The role of the modern teacher has also changed. A modern teacher is a researcher, consultant, organizer, project manager, navigator of effective work with knowledge, a "collective teacher".

The main task of the teacher is to create and organize conditions that initiate the educational activities of schoolchildren, leading to educational results that meet the new demands of society.

Thus, the consolidation and development of critical and creative thinking skills should provide an additional opportunity to increase the level of social adaptation of teachers, create additional resources necessary for the successful activity of a teacher. A critically thinking teacher can work in a more organized manner, can orient himself and orient students to the modern attitudes of society.

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